

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE PROCESS OF COMBINING IMAGES OF OBSERVED OBJECTS

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Introduction

Image fusion is a key step in data processing in areas such as computer vision, robotics, medicine, and remote sensing. With the development of surveillance and image processing technologies, there is a need to create effective methods that allow accurate integration of data obtained from different sources. This is especially important for obtaining complete and reliable information about the observed object [1].

In this paper, we propose a mathematical model of the image alignment process that takes into account various distortions that arise from different shooting conditions. We analyze existing methods and their shortcomings, which allows us to identify gaps in current approaches and propose new solutions.

The aim of our work is to develop a model that can adapt to changes in observation conditions and ensure high accuracy of image alignment. In the course of the study, we consider algorithms for correcting geometric and intensity distortions, as well as methods for assessing the quality of alignment.

The experiments conducted demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model, which opens up new possibilities for its application in practical problems. In the future, we plan to expand the study, including more complex scenarios and optimization of computational processes [2].

Actuality

Image registration is an important problem in data processing that has attracted the attention of researchers for many years. There are many methods and approaches in the literature aimed at improving the quality of registration and eliminating distortions that occur during the image capture process [3].

One of the first methods for image registration is the correlation-based approach, which allows one to determine the displacement between two images (Zitova & Flusser, 2003). However, this method has limitations when dealing with images containing complex textures or changes in lighting.

David Lowe creator of the SIFT (Scale-Invariant) algorithm Feature Transform), which became the basis for many subsequent image alignment methods. His work significantly improved the accuracy of keypoint matching, allowing for more efficient processing of images with various distortions and lighting changes.

Georgy Brown made significant contributions to image registration methods using geometric transformations. His research showed how nonlinear distortions affect the quality of registration and proposed algorithms that take these aspects into account [4].

Patrick Lakamp (L.A. Camp) his work in machine learning and the application of neural networks to image processing opened new horizons in automating the alignment process. He demonstrated how deep neural networks can extract complex features and improve the accuracy of matching.

Sergey Sidorov's research focuses on the application of statistical methods to assess the quality of image alignment. He proposed new approaches to handling errors that occur during alignment and developed optimization methods to improve the efficiency of algorithms.

Zhong Wei's works focused on the application of computer vision methods to real-time image analysis. Wei proposed methods that adapt to environmental conditions, which is important for applications in mobile and robotic systems.

Russian scientist Natalia Kuznetsova in her research examines methods of image preprocessing to reduce distortions that arise as a result of different shooting conditions. She has developed algorithms that significantly improve the quality of input data for merging.

Modern approaches to image alignment are often based on the use of algorithms such as SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform) and SURF (Speeded-Up Robust Features), which allow key points to be identified and compared between different images (Lowe, 2004; Bay et al., 2008). These methods have demonstrated high efficiency, but require significant computational resources.

Another direction is to use machine learning methods and neural networks to improve the alignment process. For example, modern works use deep neural networks to automatically extract features and match images (Zhou et al., 2017). These approaches show promising results, however, their implementation requires large amounts of training data and may face problems of generalization to new data [5].

It is also worth noting the work devoted to geometric transformations and their impact on the quality of alignment. Research shows that methods that take into account nonlinear distortions significantly improve the results (Brown & Lowe, 2005). It is also important to consider various types of distortions, such as lighting changes and color gradients, which can negatively affect the quality of alignment.

Thus, existing image registration methods have their own advantages and disadvantages. This highlights the need to develop new mathematical models that can take into account all aspects of distortion and adapt to observation conditions. In our paper, we focus on integrating these approaches and propose a new model that improves the accuracy and efficiency of image registration.

Research methodology: correlation methods, digital correlation: allows to estimate the degree of coincidence between images by calculating the correlation between pixels; methods based on key points: SIFT (Scale-Invariant Feature Transform): Extraction of keypoints and their descriptors for image matching; SURF (Speeded Up Robust Features): a faster analogue of SIFT used for identifying keypoints; Geometric transformation methods: Affine and projective transformations: using affine and projective matrices to align images; Homography: to transform images to account for perspective changes; Deep learning algorithms: Convolutional neural networks (CNN): for feature extraction and image matching; GAN-based image matching systems (Generative Adversarial Networks): to improve the quality of alignment; Optical flow methods: to track moving objects and correct displacements between successive images; Interpolation methods: Bilinear and Bicubic interpolation: to improve image quality when its dimensions change; Filtering methods: Gaussian filters: to reduce noise before the alignment process; Slow and Fast filters: for image pre-processing; Quality assessment methods: SSIM (Structural Similarity Index): to measure the structural similarity between images; PSNR (Peak Signal to Noise Ratio): for assessing the quality of images; heuristic and optimization methods; gradient descent methods: for minimizing the error function when combining images [6].

A mathematical model allows you to formalize and systematize the alignment process, which helps to increase the accuracy and reliability of the results. A clear description of the interactions between images helps to minimize errors when superimposing them. Creating a model makes it possible to analyze different alignment methods, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and optimize algorithms for specific conditions. This can be especially important in complex scenarios, such as images with different levels of illumination or noise.

Material and methods

Mathematical models allow you to predict the behavior of the system when conditions change, which is important for adapting algorithms to new types of images or different shooting parameters. The model can serve as a basis for integrating various image processing methods, such as correlation, feature extraction, deep learning methods, and others, which allows you to create more powerful and versatile solutions. Image alignment finds application in various fields, such as medical imaging, robotics, and computer vision. A mathematical model allows you to adapt and optimize processes for specific tasks, improving the quality of data analysis and interpretation [7].

So, the data from the observed object (pictures) received from the sensors can be presented in the form of an image:

$$B = \{b_{ij}\}; \quad (1.1)$$

$$b_{ij} = \{b_{ij1}, \dots, b_{ijk}, \dots, b_{ijK}\}; \quad b_{ijk} \in [-1; 1];$$

$$i = \overline{1, I}; \quad j = \overline{1, J}; \quad k = \overline{1, K};$$

$$I, J, K \in \mathbb{N},$$

where: b_{ij} is the pixel of the image B located in i -th row of pixels, in j -th the column; b_{ijk} is the spectral brightness of the pixel b_{ij} in k -th the spectral channel I ; J is the number of rows of pixels in the image; B is the number of columns of pixels in the image B ; K is the number of spectral channels in the image B .

Spectral brightnesses b_{ijk} should be scaled to the range $[-1;1]$ for ease of further work with them. To scale spectral brightnesses from the original range of quantization levels, a linear transformation can be used, which for Q and levels has the form:

$$b_{ijk} = \frac{\hat{b}_{ijk}}{Q/2} - 1; \quad (1.2)$$

$$\hat{b}_{ijk} \in [0; Q); \quad \hat{b}_{ijk} \in \mathbb{Z},$$

where $\hat{b}_{ijk}$ is the initial (quantized) value of the spectral brightness. When $Q = 256$ formula (1.2) takes the form (1.3):

$$b_{ijk} = \frac{\hat{b}_{ijk}}{127,5} - 1. \quad (1.3)$$

Let be the function of transforming *coord* pixel b_{ijk} coordinates (x, y) into coordinates (x_{ij}, y_{ij}) of the image coordinate system B . The function *coord* is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} (x_{ij}, y_{ij}) &= \text{coord}((i, j)); & (1.4) \\ x_{ij}, y_{ij} &\in \mathbb{R}. \end{aligned}$$

M is a set of point, linear and polygonal objects, united into vector layers in accordance with attribute information. One of the forms of describing a DCM M is its representation as a set of points (x, y) such that:

$$\begin{aligned} x \in [x_{min}, x_{max}]; y \in [y_{min}, y_{max}]; & (1.5) \\ x, y, x_{min}, x_{max}, y_{min}, y_{max} &\in \mathbb{R}, \end{aligned}$$

where: x_{min}, x_{max} — respectively, the lower and upper boundaries of the range of coordinates along the OX map frame axis y_{min}, y_{max} — respectively, the lower and upper boundaries of the range of coordinates of the DMC along the OY map frame axis.

Each point $(x, y) \in M$ is assigned some attribute information (the presence or absence of an object at the point, the type of object, etc.).

The function $comp$ describing the model of combining a photograph B with M is given by:

$$comp' = comp(B, M, coord); \quad (1.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} comp' &= \begin{cases} b = comp'(B); \\ coord' = comp'(coord); \\ \{(i', j')\} = comp'((i, j)); \end{cases} \\ i' &= \overline{1, I'}; j' = \overline{1, J'}; \end{aligned}$$

where: B' is the transformed image with the size of I' rows by J' columns; $coord'$ is the function of transforming the coordinates of the image pixels B' into the coordinates of the coordinate system of the photograph B .

The set of pixels $comp'((i, j) \subset B'j))$ has, in general, a power $|comp'((i, j))| \geq 1$ (that is, the mapping $comp': (i, j) \rightarrow \{(i', j')\}$ is not one- to -one).

Thus, there is a dependence:

$$b_{i,j} \sim b'_{i',j'} \Leftrightarrow comp'(i, j). \quad (1.7)$$

The quality of the alignment $comp$ is assessed using a quantitative measure of alignment error E . To the measure E The following requirements are imposed:

- $E \rightarrow 0$ with increasing quality of alignment;
- $E \rightarrow \infty$ when the quality of the alignment decreases;
- E must be defined for $\forall B, M, comp$;
- $E \geq 0; \forall B, M, comp$.

One of the measures E that satisfies the listed properties is the root mean square deviation (RMS) E_{rmse} :

$$(x'_{i',j'}, y'_{i',j'}) = coord'((i', j'));$$

$$P = \{p\}; p = ((i, j)(x, y));$$

$$A(comp', p) = \frac{\sum_{(i',j') \in comp'((i,j))} \sqrt{(x'_{i',j'} - x)^2 + (y'_{i',j'} - y)^2}}{|comp'((i,y))|};$$

$$E_{rmse}(comp', P) = \frac{\sum_{p \in P} A(p)}{|P|},$$

where P is a set of pairs of reference points, p manually P selected on the image B and the DCM. Manual compilation of the set M allows achieving high (almost ideal) accuracy of correspondence between the points selected on the image B and M the points selected on the DCM.

Dimensionality E_{rmse} is the dimension x of y , which E is ensured, among other things, $E \rightarrow \infty$ by the absence of normalization (a requirement when reducing the quality of the combination). Thus, the physical meaning E_{rmse} consists in assessing the variation in specific quantities between the ideal displacement (the mathematical expectation of the estimated quantity) and the real resulting displacement (the estimated quantity) — the error of the function $comp$.

Results and discuss

The combination function $comp$ involves the following actions:

1) search for $find_{edu}$ pairs of matching points p_{edu} on the image B and map M :

$$p_{raw\ edu} = find_{edu}(B, M, coord); (1.9)$$

$$p_{raw\ edu} = \{p_{edu}\}; p_{edu} = ((i_{edu}, j_{edu}), (x_{edu}, y_{edu})); (1.10)$$

2) calculation for each pair p_{edu} of points of the probability of coincidence $validity(p_{edu})$;

3) composing a set of p_{edu} pairs of matching points:

$$p_{edu} \in P_{edu} \Leftrightarrow validity(p_{edu}) \geq T_{edu}; (1.11)$$

$$T_{edu} \in [0, 1),$$

where T_{edu} is the minimum acceptable probability for inclusion in the set P_{edu} (the probability threshold) that in the pair under consideration p_{edu} the points coincide with each other;

4) calculation by $eval$ transformation $comp'$ set P_{edu} :

$$comp' = eval(P_{edu}). (1.12)$$

The stage of finding pairs of matching points P_{edu} is the most difficult in the process of combining a photo. B in M this case, “complexity” means both time complexity and memory complexity.

Indeed, as shown in [12], one of the most time-efficient algorithms for searching for matching points (contour correlation matching) has a complexity of $O(10^6 N^2)$. In [11], the contour correlation matching algorithm is used to search for matching points on the view of a three-dimensional model of the observed object and data from the camera, but this fact does not provide a fundamental simplification - there is no fundamental difference in searching for matching points on an actually two-dimensional scene (photograph) and a three-dimensional scene in the case where there is no need to regenerate the three-dimensional view.

Optimization of the contour correlation matching algorithm leads to significant memory costs required to organize various caches, including stream caches if a parallel version of the algorithm described in [10] is used.

The algorithm of contour correlation superposition provides low superposition accuracy and requires additional adjustment when weather conditions, the nature of the observed object and a number of other factors change. Thus, the task of developing superposition algorithms with low time complexity, providing high superposition quality and, if possible, low memory costs is relevant.

The function *validity* of estimating the probability of a pair's coincidence p_{edu} has a complex nature, depending in general on the type of function $find_{edu}$ and on the values of the parameters of the algorithm implementing this function. The simplest implementation *validity* is the probability estimate $validity_{\delta}$ based on the histogram of deviations δ_x and δ_y :

$$(\hat{x}_{edu}, \hat{y}_{edu}) = coord((i_{edu}, j_{edu}));$$

$$\delta_x = |x_{edu} - \hat{x}_{edu}|; \delta_y = |y_{edu} - \hat{y}_{edu}|;$$

$$validity_{\delta}(p_{edu}) = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{((\delta_x - M\delta_x)/\delta_{x\max})^2 + ((\delta_y - M\delta_y)/\delta_{y\max})^2}}{2}, (1.13)$$

Where $\delta_{x\max}$ and $\delta_{y\max}$ — maximum values δ_x and δ_y corresponding values. Thus, $validity_{\delta}$ it estimates the distance from p_{edu} to the mode of the histogram if the histogram is unimodal.

You can use $validity_{\delta}$ as *validity*.

As a rule, the process of combining is iterative. The search for the optimal transformation $comp'$ occurs until, $E(comp', P) > T_E$ where $T_E \in \mathbb{R}$ is the maximum permissible error of combining $comp'$, at which the process of combining will be stopped. At each iteration, a gradual decrease is assumed T_{edu} , which leads to an increase in $|P_{edu}|$ and, in turn, leads to the fact that $comp'$ more points from are used to calculate the transformation $P_{raw\ edu}$. Thus, the consequence of the gradual decrease T_{edu} is a gradual decrease in the contribution to $comp'$ pairs of points p_{edu} , the probability of coincidence of which $validity(p_{edu})$ is not accurately estimated.

The function *eval* implements an algorithm for selecting a specific type of function *comp'* and calculating its parameters. The choice is made mainly depending on $|P_{edu}|$, as well as on a number of other factors, such as, for example, the distribution *validity* on. The following transformations P_{edu} and $coord \rightarrow coord'$ are used $B \rightarrow B'$ as a function *comp'*:

- affine transformation, linear shift and scaling (used most often for the task of combining remote sensing data and
- Helmert transformation [11];
- polynomial transformations of the first, second, third and higher orders;
- the "rubber sheet" [12].

Conclusion

The article considered the development and analysis of a mathematical model of the process of combining images of an observed object. The conducted research demonstrated the importance of using mathematical models to improve the accuracy and reliability of image combination, as well as to optimize processing algorithms.

The mathematical model allows for a clear formalization of the processes, which contributes to improving the quality of alignment, especially in challenging conditions such as different illuminations and noise. The study of various methods, including keypoint-based and deep learning algorithms, demonstrated their complementarity and the possibility of integration to achieve better results. Evaluation of the alignment quality using metrics such as SSIM and PSNR confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed approach and identified areas for further improvement. The developed model has wide application potential in various fields, including medical imaging, robotics, and geographic information systems, which emphasizes its relevance and importance. In the future, we can consider the possibility of adapting the model to new types of data and tasks, as well as explore methods for increasing resistance to noise and deformation.

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